

Using Machine Learning Methods to Estimate Sea Surface DMS Concentration for Studying Seabird Movements

Meixuan Liu^{*1}, Fernando Benitez-Paez^{†1}, Oliver Padget^{‡2}, Dmitry Kishkinev^{§3}
and Urška Demšar^{**1}

¹ School of Geography and Sustainable Development, University of St Andrews

²Department of Earth, Ocean and Ecological Sciences, University of Liverpool

³School of Life Sciences, Keele University

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Summary

Dimethylsulphide (DMS) has been shown to play a vital role in foraging behaviour of seabirds and suggested as a key component of olfactory navigation, yet its spatial distribution remains poorly understood due to limited point-based sampling. This study evaluates five machine learning algorithms and three ensemble models to estimate sea surface DMS concentrations in the North Atlantic using remote-sensing sources. XGBoost and an ensemble model incorporating ridge regression indicate high accuracy and outperform other methods. Also, models reflect that DMS levels are strongly influenced by nitrate and chlorophyll-a, aligning with their chemical properties and increasing the reliability of the model. The proposed approach aims to provide accurate, high-resolution DMS concentration estimates to support future research on avian olfactory navigation.

KEYWORDS: Dimethylsulphide (DMS), Remote Sensing, Machine Learning, Animal Movement

1. Introduction

Dimethylsulphide (DMS) is a volatile organic compound (VOC) derived from dimethylsulfoniopropionate (DMSP), synthesized by phytoplankton and transferred from water to the atmosphere through thermodynamic processes. As a critical aerosol in the sulphur cycle, DMS can adjust the radiation budget of the Earth and reflects local marine productivity, serving as an indicator of albedo and trophic state.

Beyond its significance in climate regulation, the distinctive odour of DMS plays a role in finding food patches for seabirds, and also potentially vital in long-distance navigation through constructing olfactory gradient maps. Dell'Arriccia et al. (2014) demonstrated that shearwaters are attracted to DMS across various temperate oceans, likely as a foraging cue. Zannoni et al. (2020) further supported the potential role of VOCs in bird navigation in establishing homing olfactory maps. However, the role of olfactory cues in long-distance migrating seabirds remains challenging to study, as linking bird tracking data to DMS distributions requires high-resolution, spatially extensive DMS datasets, which are currently unavailable.

Previous attempts to model DMS distributions have relied on geophysical-chemical and climatological approaches. Since 2018, classical machine learning techniques have been employed to estimate DMS concentrations at regional and global scales, but with coarse spatio-temporal resolutions (Bell, 2021;

* ml340@st-andrews.ac.uk

† Fernando.Benitez@st-andrews.ac.uk

‡ oliver.padget@liverpool.ac.uk

§ d.kishkinev@keele.ac.uk

** urska.demsar@st-andrews.ac.uk

McNabb & Tortell, 2022). Mansour et al. (2023) employed Gaussian Process Regression to achieve accurate predictions, though within limited domains.

This study evaluates the performance of individual machine learning algorithms and ensemble models in predicting sea surface DMS concentrations across the North Atlantic. The aim is to identify the best-performing models capable of generating fine-resolution DMS maps. These maps will facilitate integration with avian movement data, advancing the understanding of olfactory navigation in seabirds.

2. Method

2.1. Study area & Data Source

This study evaluates the use of machine learning to estimate sea surface DMS concentrations in the North Atlantic (NA), focusing on a pilot area (60°W–30°W, 40°N–60°N) during July 2011 (**Figure 1**). The test domain was selected based on the availability of DMS data. The workflow is summarised in **Figure 2**, and experiments were performed using Python.

Predictor variables were selected based on the multilinear regression results of Mansour et al. (2023), as detailed in **Table 1**. DMS data in-situ point measurements were sourced from NOAA-PMEL (Pacific Marine Environmental Laboratory) and NASA-NAAMES (North Atlantic Aerosols and Marine Ecosystems Study) databases. NOAA-PMEL provides global DMS observations, while NASA-NAAMES focuses on regional cruises in the North-West Atlantic.

Table 1 Variables

Predictor Variable	Response Variable
Chlorophyll-a (CHL)	Sea Surface DMS Concentration
Mixed Layer Depth (MLD)	
Sea Surface Temperature (SST)	
Nitrate (NO ₃)	
Photosynthetically Available Radiation (PAR)	

Environmental data for the first 4 variables were obtained from Copernicus Model Level 4 (L4) products, which offer gridded, calibrated, and validated datasets while PAR data were obtained from NASA MODIS-Aqua at Level 3 (L3) mapped resolution. All datasets were daily, with a spatial resolution of 4 km, except for NO₃ (0.25°). Missing PAR values due to orbital gaps were addressed using 8-daily averages.

Figure 1. The map of the study area, where locates in the north-west of the North Atlantic Ocean.

Figure 2. Workflow of the experiment utilising remote sensing and machine learning modelling. The process includes data integration, spatial-temporal alignment, model tuning and evaluation, and application to grid-based estimations.

2.2. Preprocessing & Feature Engineering

Data preprocessing involved masking PAR datasets to exclude inland water bodies and interpolate missing values using 8-daily averages. For remote sensing data, a mask was applied to ensure inland water bodies were excluded from marine PAR calculations (**Figure 3**). Then a daily trend was extracted via wavelet transform filtering, and smoothed by a Gaussian filter at data edges (**Figure 4**).

To align predictor and target variables spatially and temporally, K-D Trees were constructed. For each DMS point, the four nearest spatio-temporal neighbours were identified, and values were interpolated using Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) (**Figure 5**), also enabling the generation of fine daily DMS grids (1 km).

Figure 3. Masking in PAR. Land area (orange) is being masked from analysis on the ocean (dark blue). The area with missing data (light blue) was processed to be identifiable.

Figure 4. Filtering method in PAR. Temporal trend from t1 to t8 was extracted and 8-daily data were accordingly adapted and smoothed by wavelet transform and gaussian filter to fill the missing area.

Figure 5. Interpolation by searching neighbours. The values of the variable from the four nearest spatio-temporal neighbours (light blue) were identified and the value of the target data point (orange) was calculated and assigned by IDW.

2.3. Algorithms

The predictor variables (CHL, MLD, SST, NO₃, PAR) were standardized to address scale differences and the target variable was DMS. The dataset was split into training and testing subsets (7:3), with hyperparameter optimisation conducted through grid and random search using 10-fold and 5-fold cross-validation.

Single machine learning models included Gaussian Process Regression, Random Forest, XGBoost, Support Vector Machine, and Artificial Neural Networks, chosen for their regression suitability and proven performance from previous studies. Model evaluation relied on R² and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), with overfitting carefully monitored.

To enhance model generalisability for large-scale NA applications, ensemble models were tested using stacking with three meta-models (**Figure 2**). Additionally, SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) analysis was conducted to assess predictor variable contributions and dependencies, improving model interpretability.

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. Model Performance

Figure 6 compares the performance of the single algorithms. XGBoost consistently outperformed the other models, achieving the highest R² (0.853) and lowest RMSE (0.78), without signs of overfitting. This indicates that XGBoost explains 85.3% of the variance in DMS concentration, and its RMSE of 0.78 is relatively low compared to the standard deviation of the original dataset (2.026). The model demonstrated strong predictive capabilities across the value range, as illustrated in **Figure 7**, where it demonstrated superior ability to capture and predict distributed values compared to the other algorithms.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. Comparison of the performance by single models. Metrics for assessment were (a) RMSE and (b) R^2 . The models are Gaussian Process Regression (GPR), Random Forest (RF), XGBoost (XGB), Support Vector Regression (SVR) and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP).

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

Figure 7. Observed vs Predicted DMS distribution, indicating the difference between model predicted and observed values for each DMS data point, and the ability of the model to capture and predict values in each range. The closer the points are to the red dotted line, the better the predicted values align with the observed values. (a) MLP. (b) SVR. (c) XGBoost. (d) GPR. (e) RF.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 8. Results of ensembled models. The line graphs (a) MSE & (b) R^2 show iterative records of the performance of the ensembled models under the three meta-models in a five-fold cross-validation, with their means of the metrics calculated separately. The stacked model with Ridge Regression as the meta model performs the best. (c) The scatter plot indicates the predictive power of the best-performing model. The closer the blue points are to the red dotted line, the better the predicted values agree with the observed values.

For ensemble models, the stacking model with ridge regression as the meta-model demonstrated the best performance, with a mean R^2 of 0.843 and a mean RMSE of 0.802. Although its RMSE is slightly higher than XGBoost, it displayed a stronger ability to predict larger DMS values (**Figure 8**). Given this advantage, the ridge regression-based stacking model is a viable option for future predictions of DMS concentrations over larger spatial domains.

3.2. Feature Contributions and Model Interpretability

The SHAP analysis results (**Figure 9**) revealed that nitrate (NO_3) and chlorophyll-a (CHL) were the most significant predictors of DMS concentrations, while photosynthetically available radiation (PAR) had minimal influence. This observation aligns with the partial dependence plot, which shows that variations in PAR have a negligible impact on the global model output. These findings are chemically consistent, as NO_3 and CHL are closely linked to phytoplankton productivity, a primary source of DMS.

(a)

Figure 9. SHAP plot and Partial dependence plot of the features according to XGB. (a) The SHAP plots demonstrate the variable dependency and can help to increase the explainability of the model, illustrating the features' impact on the model's predictions. Each dot represents an observation, with high feature values in pink and low feature values in blue. Features are ranked by importance, with the most influential at the top. (b) The partial dependence plot shows the average marginal effect of a feature on the model's prediction while holding other features constant. It reflects how changes in the feature influence the predicted outcome on average, helping to understand the feature's overall contribution to the model's behavior.

3.3. Generalisation and Comparison with Previous Studies

The generalisation results (**Figure 10**) demonstrate the generalisation of point-based DMS observations to a gridded spatial domain by estimation, with XGBoost and the ridge regression stacking model effectively capturing spatial variability. The study's models significantly outperform previous methods: the GPR model ($R^2 = 0.67$) from Mansour et al. (2023), the ANN model ($R^2 = 0.59$) from McNabb & Tortell (2022), and the RF model ($R^2 = 0.65$) from Bell (2021). The enhanced performance may be attributed to the geospatial preprocessing techniques applied in this study, including advanced filtering and interpolation on remote sensing data, as opposed to simpler binning approaches used in previous research.

Figure 10. Generalisation output of DMS estimation on (a) 1st July 2011; (b) 15th July 2011; (c) 31st July 2011. The output of the generalisation is a raster with a spatial resolution of 1km. The beginning, middle and end of the month have been chosen to illustrate the temporal variations of the model's estimation in a short term.

4. Conclusion & Future Work

The paper combines the machine learning approach with remote sensing resources and techniques, leveraging efficient and highly performed algorithms, which is vital yet rarely applied in seabird navigation. Both the XGBoost and the stacked model with Ridge Regression achieve high accuracy and highlight the strong influence of nitrate and chlorophyll-a on DMS levels, reinforcing their reliability. By utilising remote sensing data, this approach provides a scalable solution to overcome the limitations of point-based sampling.

Building upon the findings of this study, future research will focus on extending the estimation of DMS concentrations to the entire NA using the XGBoost model and the ensemble model with ridge regression, and developing the pipeline into an automated computational package capable of generating daily sea surface DMS concentration maps at a 1 km resolution. Integrated with avian trajectory data, this will enable a novel data-driven investigation into the role of DMS in seabird navigation, specifically examining whether Manx shearwaters (*Puffinus puffinus*) use DMS gradients for navigation between colonies and foraging areas (**Figure 11**). The study lays the groundwork for advancing ecological research on olfactory navigation using real-world movement and environmental data.

Figure 11. Foraging trips of GPS-tracked Manx shearwaters from the Copeland Islands, with homing trips in blue bold.

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Biographies

Meixuan Liu, is a PhD candidate at School of Geography and Sustainable Development (SGSD), University of St Andrews. Her research interest lies in spatio-temporal analytics applied to avian ecology and climate data.

Fernando Benitez-Paez, is a Lecturer in SGSD. His research interest lies in geoinformatics and geo-development, specialising in urban analytics and data fusion.

Oliver Padget, is a Royal Society University Research Fellow and proleptic lecturer at Department of Earth, Ocean and Ecological Sciences, School of Environmental Sciences, University of Liverpool. His research interest lies in using tracking technology to investigate all aspects of bird behaviours and migratory patterns.

Dmitry Kishkinev, is a Lecturer at School of Life Sciences, Keele University. He is a movement ecologist studying animal orientation and navigation and sensory mechanisms underlying those particularly in birds.

Urška Demšar, is Senior Lecturer at School of Geography and Sustainable Development, University of St Andrews. Her research interest lies in spatio-temporal analytics and movement analysis, covering both demographic and animal movement study.